

ALGORITHM FOR LISTING OF SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITIONS

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ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION (SFP) , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r) = F'(N)$,where

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

In this note an algorithm to list out all the SFPs of a number without missing any is developed.

DISCUSSION:

DEFINITION: $F'_x(y)$ is defined as the number of those SFPs of y which involve terms not greater than x .

If F_1 be a factor partition of y :

$F_1 \rightarrow x_1 \times x_2 \times x_3 \times \dots \times x_r$, then F_1 is included in $F'_x(y)$ iff

$$x_i \leq x \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq r$$

clearly $F'_x(y) \leq F'(y)$, The equality holds good iff $x \geq y$.

Example: $F'_8(24) = 5$. Out of 7 only the last 5 are included in $F'_8(24)$.

- (1) 24
- (2) 12 X 2
- (3) 8 X 3
- (4) 6 X 4
- (5) 6 X 2 X 2
- (6) 4 X 3 X 2
- (7) 3 X 2 X 2 X 2.

ALGORITHM: Let $d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_r$ be the divisors of N in descending order. For listing the factor partitions following are the steps:

(A) (1) Start with $d_1 = N$.

(2) Write all the factor partitions involving d_2 and so on.

(B) While listing care should be taken that the terms from left to right should be written in descending order.

** At $d_k \geq N^{1/2} \geq d_{k+1}$, and onwards, step (B) will ensure that there is no repetition.

Example: $N = 36$, Divisors are 36, 18, 12, 9, 6, 4, 3, 2, 1.

- 36 ----> 36
- 18 ----> 18 X 2
- 12 ----> 12 X 3
- 9 ----> 9 X 4
- 9 X 2 X 2
- 6 ----> 6 X 6
- 6 ----> 6 X 3 X 2
- $d_k = N^{1/2}$
- 4 ----> 4 X 3 X 3

3 --->3 X 3 X 2 X 2
 2 --->NIL
 1 --->NIL

FORMULA FOR F'(N)

$$F'(N) = \sum_{d_r/N} F'_{d_r}(N/d_r) \quad \text{-----(8.1)}$$

Example:

$$N = 216 = 2^3 3^3$$

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|----------------------------|------------------------------|
| (1) 216 | --->F ₂₁₆ (1) = 1 |
| (2) 108 X 2 | --->F ₁₀₈ (2) = 1 |
| (3) 72 X 3 | --->F ₇₂ (3) = 1 |
| (4) 54 X 4 | --->F ₅₄ (4) = 2 |
| (5) 54 X 2 X 2 | |
| (6) 36 X 6 | --->F ₃₆ (6) = 2 |
| (7) 36 X 3 X 2 | |
| (8) 27 X 8 | --->F ₂₇ (8) = 3 |
| (9) 27 X 4 X 2 | |
| (10) 27 X 2 X 2 X 2 | |
| (11) 24 X 9 | --->F ₂₄ (9) = 2 |
| (12) 24 X 3 X 3 | |
| (13) 18 X 12 | --->F ₁₈ (12) = 4 |
| (14) 18 X 6 X 2 | |
| (15) 18 X 4 X 3 | |
| (16) 18 X 3 X 2 X 2 | |
| (17) 12 X 9 X 2 | --->F ₁₂ (18) = 3 |
| (18) 12 X 6 X 3 | |
| (19) 12 X 3 X 3 X 2 | |
| (20) 9 X 8 X 3 | --->F ₉ (24) = 5 |
| (21) 9 X 6 X 4 | |
| (22) 9 X 6 X 2 X 2 | |
| (23) 9 X 4 X 3 X 2 | |
| (24) 9 X 3 X 2 X 2 | |
| (25) 8 X 3 X 3 X 3 | --->F ₈ (27) = 1 |
| (26) 6 X 6 X 6 | --->F ₆ (36) = 4 |
| (27) 6 X 6 X 3 X 2 | |
| (28) 6 X 4 X 3 X 3 | |
| (29) 6 X 3 X 3 X 2 X 2 | |
| (30) 4 X 3 X 3 X 3 X 2 X 2 | --->F ₄ (54) = 1 |
| (31) 3 X 3 X 3 X 2 X 2 X 2 | --->F ₃ (72) = 1 |
| | --->F ₂ (108) = 0 |
| | --->F ₁ (216) = 0 |

$$F'(216) = \sum_{d_r/N} F'_{d_r}(216/d_r) = 31$$

Remarks: This algorithm would be quite helpfull in developing a computer program for the listing of SFPs.

REFERENCES:

- [1] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'Generalization Of Partition Function, Introducing 'Smarandache Factor Partition', SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [2] " The Florentine Smarandache " Special Collection, Archives of American Mathematics, Centre for American History, University of Texas at Austin, USA.